

The Modelling of Failure Processes and the Role of the Matrix in the Failure of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Resin

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ABSTRACT

The effect of changing resin systems on the rate of damage accumulation in carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin has been studied. Damage has been monitored by acoustic emission and the experimental results compared to a mathematical model of damage accumulation. The model had previously been able to quantify differences in damage rate obtained with different fibre arrangements and in this study is shown to be able to quantify differences due to different resin systems.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (c f r p) has been shown to continue to accumulate internal damage under steady loading conditions (1). This is the case for unidirectional specimens loaded in the fibre direction, cross plied plates and internally pressurised vessels (2). Although traditional monitoring techniques such as extensometry are unable to detect creep of unidirectional specimens acoustic emissions has proved a means by which these failure processes can be detected. The acoustic emission technique has provided a surprisingly reliable means of quantifying damage accumulation in this material and when combined with a model of composite failure based on the viscoelastic properties of the resin, provides a potentially powerful means of studying failure processes.

Failure model

A model of damage accumulation in unidirectional c f r p loaded in the fibre direction has been proposed and shown to be applicable to a number of different structures including filament wound tubes (3). It is assumed that the carbon fibres are perfectly elastic and that an unidirectional c f r p specimen can be considered to be a fibre bundle embedded in a viscoelastic matrix. The effect of load transfer by the shear of the matrix isolates fibre breaks in a narrow section of the composite so that the Rosen model of a chain in which the links are fibre bundles and their lengths are determined by the load transfer length can be applied (4). It has been shown that as damage is accumulated in a fibre bundle the load which can be safely supported without causing catastrophic failure passes through a maximum (3). At loads lower than the simple tensile

strength of the bundle the specimen can support a greater degree of damage than at the maximum load. The form of the damage load curve is given by:

$$P = (N_o - N_f) f_o \left[L_n \left(\frac{N_o}{(N_o - N_f)} \right) \right]^{1/\delta} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load
 N_f the number of broken fibres
 f the load applied to each fibre
 f_o a constant
 δ Weibull shape parameter

Figure 1: The theoretical failure behaviour of an elastic fibre bundle if fibres are broken whilst the bundle is held under constant load.

Figure 1 shows the curve given by equation 1. If at a given steady load P_1 a mechanism intervenes to produce further fibre failures, even though the load remains steady, damage will be accumulated along the line A, B. Acoustic emission reveals that further damage is accumulated and that if further loading takes place after having reached the damage level A_2 a quiet period is observed. It has been shown (3) that this observation demonstrates that the accumulated damage is the progressive failure of the weakest fibres in the composite. The rate of damage accumulation must depend on the matrix properties so that a mathematical description of the failure scenario should reveal differences if the matrix properties are modified.

Under steady loading conditions damage accumulation in most plate and some filament wound structures, as revealed by acoustic emission monitoring, is described by the relation:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{A}{(t+\tau)^n} \quad (2)$$

in which N is the emission count
 t the time
 τ a time constant
 n a power less than 1

and A is a parameter which depends only of the applied load so is constant for steady loading conditions.

The value of n for unidirectional specimens is very close to 1 being 0.99 however as the fibre arrangement is changed so as to introduce the possibility of failure mechanisms other than fibre breakage and also permitting greater freedom of movement of the resin the value of n decreases. In this way it is seen that n is 0.98 for $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$ cfrp, 0.95 for $(\pm 15^\circ)$ specimens and 0.90 for $(0^\circ, 90^\circ, T)$ specimens in which T refers to a woven cloth layer. The theoretical behaviour of the resin is seen therefore to be a great importance.

If n is put equal to 1 and equation 2 integrated we see that

$$N = A \log \left(\frac{t+\tau}{\tau} \right) \quad (3)$$

so that from equation 2 and 3 we obtain

$$\log \left(\frac{dt}{dN} \right) = \frac{N}{A} + \log \frac{\tau}{A} \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 shows therefore that under steady loading $\log \left(\frac{dt}{dN} \right)$ is a linear function of the accumulated emission and that the slope of the curve obtained is $1/A$.

For specimens made from the Fibredux 914 C Ciba-Geigy prepreg the parameter A has been shown to obey a relation of the form

$$A = \lambda e^{k\sigma} \quad (5)$$

where σ is the applied stress
and λ and k are constants

Experimentals details

Experiments have been conducted on flat unnotched plate specimens made from two types of prepreg. These were Ciba Geigy's Fibredux 914 CTS which has a curing temperature of 180°C and the Toray prepreg P 350 which is cured at 120°C . These rectangular specimens were made ($17 \times 230 \times 0.4$ mm) from three layers of prepreg with steel tabs bonded to them to give a gauge length of 100 mm. The specimens had a fibre volume fraction of the order of 60% and were made in an autoclave.

Constant load tests were conducted at different load levels on a Mayes creep machine loaded by dead weights on a cantilevered arm pivoted to give a load gain of 15 : 1.

All acoustic emission monitoring was made with a 3000 series Dunegan-Endevco system with a PZT-5 differential transducer, type 140 B with a dominant frequency at 200 KHz, a preamplifier of 40 dB with filters providing a gate of 100 KHz to 300 KHz, an amplifier with adjustable gain and an impulse detector transforming all peaks exceeding 1 V at the output into digital pulses. An envelope processor grouped together all events occurring in periods of 100 μs . Emission counting could be either cumulative or as a rate by resetting to zero at regular intervals.

As earlier studies had revealed a nearly logarithmic periodmeter was developed. This allowed the logarithm of the time necessary for counting a given number of emissions $\log (dt/dN)$ to be recorded as a function of the total number of emissions, N . Tests were conducted using a gain of 85 dB.

Experimental results

At room temperature (21°C) and relative humidity of 50% both types of cfrp continued to emit under constant loading conditions. Figures 2 and 3 show however that the rate of emission obtained with respectively the 914 C and the P 305 specimens shown in figure 2 give a value for n of 0.99 the P 305 resulted in a value of n of 0.94. The form of the curve $\log dt/dN$ as a function of N is extremely sensitive to the value of n and although at first glance the difference of 0.05 in the value of n appears small in reality it is highly significant. It has been found that the value of n for the 914 C specimens remained constant at all load levels which generated sufficient emissions to allow detailed analysis. This was found not to be the case for the P 305 specimens above about 90% of breaking stress where the value of n was calculated to be around 0.8 indicating considerable acceleration of internal damage accumulation.

Fig 2: Acoustic emission rate for a 914 unidirectional specimen during a creep test performed at 1180 MPa.

Fig 3: Acoustic emission rate for a P 305 unidirectional specimen showing a characteristic decrease in the value of n ($\sigma = 1350$ MPa).

The difference between the two resin systems is also revealed in the variation of the parameter A with applied stress. Figure 4 shows that the 914 C specimens exhibited behaviour which was described by equation 5 except at very low loads. As has been pointed out elsewhere (3) a finer expression for A is

$$A = \lambda \sinh K\sigma \tag{6}$$

but at most loads equation 6 reduces to equation 5 which is simple to manipulate. These equations describe a linear relationship between $\log A$ and the applied stress but this is not observed with the P 305 specimens.

Figure 4: Variation of the parameter A as a function of the applied stress for 914 and P 305 materials.

The differences between the two specimen types were most probably due to differences in the rheological characteristics of the two resin systems. In order to see if the behaviour of the 914 C specimens could be modified specimens were made with a lower fibre volume fraction of 30% which allowed greater freedom of movement for the resin.

Figure 5 shows the effect of reducing the fibre volume fraction. It can be seen that the relationship $\log dt/dN$ is no longer a linear function of N and a value of n of 0.97 was calculated.

Figure 5: Acoustic activity versus cumulated emissions during a creep test ($\sigma = 784$ PMa) for 914 materials ($V_f = 30\%$).

DISCUSSION

The present study continues experiments which have been conducted over a number of years mainly on specimens made from Fibredux 914 C and which have as a goal the understanding of the failure processes in cfrp and to extend this understanding to the prediction of behaviour of pressure vessels under load. Under both cyclic and steady loading reproducible acoustic emission activity has been observed which suggests a stabilisation of the failure processes (1).

The observation that even the unidirectional cfrp is not perfectly elastic is important and, as the carbon fibres are known to be elastic, reveals the role of the viscoelastic nature of the resin in damage accumulation.

It has been shown that as the fibre arrangement in the specimen is modified with respect to the unidirectional case the emission activity is changed in a quantifiable manner, shown as the variation of the power n in equation 2, (5). It has been suggested that as failure mechanisms other than fibre breakage play an increasingly important role in the failure of the composite the value of n decreases from 1. The present study has shown that by changing the resin system the same effect may be observed as is the case if the fibre volume fraction is lowered.

The P 305 specimens showed under steady conditions that damage continued to accumulate at a faster rate than was observed with the 914 C specimens and that there was less tendency to approach a pseudo-stable situation. The physical processes involved in damage accumulation under steady loads in unidirectional materials are unknown. Lifshitz and Rotem (6) suggest that the effects of fibre breaks are distributed over greater lengths of the specimen due to the relaxation of the shear stresses transferring load back into the fibre around the break. In this way fibre breaks which were originally isolated could interact or produce delayed failures at weak points in neighbouring fibres. If this is the process involved it suggests that the P 305 specimens had a resin which relaxed more quickly in the vicinity of fibre breaks than was the case for the 914 C specimens. The greater freedom of movement available to the low fibre volume fraction 914 C specimens could also account for the similar observed behaviour.

CONCLUSION

The rate of damage accumulation under steady loading conditions of unidirectional cfrp can be modified by changing the resin system used. It was found that the specimens made from P 305 prepreg showed less tendency to stabilise than did the 914 C, suggesting a greater degree of relaxation of the resin around fibre breaks in the P 305 composite.

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